

U N D E R P I N

DATA SPACE FOR MANUFACTURING

Pan-European data space for holistic asset management in critical manufacturing industries

D4.2 Use case validation and lessons learned – final report

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CCAЕ	Conditional Convolutional AutoEncoder
DAPS	Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service
DS	Data Space
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IDS-RAM	International Data Spaces Reference Architecture Model
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCL	Lower control limit
LKD	Lightning Key Data
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error
Median APE	Median Absolute Percentage Error
ML	Machine Learning
NaN	Not a Number
N-HITS	Neural Hierarchical Interpolation for Time Series
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PMaaS	Predictive Maintenance as a Service
QRM	Quantile Regression Model
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	RDF Schema
REST	Representational State Transfer
RIN	Reversible Instance Normalization
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RPA	Robotic Process Automation
RPM	Revolutions per Minute
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
TFT	Temporal Fusion Transformer
TIDE	Temporal Dynamics Embedding
UC	Use Case
UCL	Upper control limit
UI	User Interface
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WF	Wind Farm
WMAPE	Weighted Mean Absolute Percentage Error
WT	Wind Turbine

Executive summary

This document reports on the implementation of the use cases (UCs) that form the core of the UNDERPIN project, following their identification and planning, as reported in deliverable D4.1: “*Use case planning report*”. The present document builds upon the initial version of D4.2: “Use case validation and lessons learned”, hereby labelled as “mid-term report”, submitted in M12, reflecting on the efforts of tasks T4.2: “Use case trials execution” and T4.3: “Trials performance evaluation and lessons learned”.

The primary goal of the document is to provide a comprehensive overview of the UNDERPIN use cases, detailing the implementation, validation, and outcomes. It presents the final results of the use case activities and highlights the lessons learned, offering insights that can inform future decisions and steps for scaling and replicating the UNDERPIN approach in similar industrial settings. The UCs that were selected in order to showcase the functionality and benefits of UNDERPIN are presented in the following table:

Identifier	Title	Pilot
UC1.1	Monitoring and predictive maintenance in the refinery	Refinery
UC2.1	Predictive maintenance in wind farms	Wind farms
UC2.2	Wind turbine blade repair prediction	Wind farms

Each use case demonstrates the practical benefits of integrating predictive maintenance services within the UNDERPIN Data Space architecture, highlighting the added value for stakeholders, lessons learned, and key takeaways for future deployment. The deliverable also consolidates validation activities, ensuring the infrastructure is capable of supporting seamless, secure, and scalable data exchange for predictive maintenance tasks across different industrial domains.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

UNDERPIN is a manufacturing Data Space (DS) that facilitates the efficient use of industrial data with a focus on dynamic asset management and predictive maintenance procedures. Through providing a trusted platform for data sharing and exchange, UNDERPIN will foster the collaboration between large industry players and SMEs in a bid to improve products, services, as well as business operations of the involved parties.

To showcase this potential, a set of use cases (UCs) has been identified, planned, and implemented over the course of the project. Building upon the work presented in D4.1: “Use Case Planning Report” and the interim results documented in D4.2: “Use Case Validation and Lessons Learned – Mid-term Report”, the present deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the implementation, validation, and outcomes of the three identified UCs.

This final report consolidates and expands upon the findings of the mid-term version, providing the conclusive assessment of the UC activities at the completion of the project (M24). It presents the final results of the work performed in the context of T4.2: “Use Case Trials Execution” and T4.3: “Trials Performance Evaluation and Lessons Learned”, summarizing the key findings, validation outcomes, and lessons learned derived from the trials. Beyond reporting on the individual UC achievements, this document also aims to distil insights and recommendations that can serve as guidance for future adopters, both within UNDERPIN and in other DS initiatives, seeking to replicate or build upon the demonstrated approaches.

1.2 UNDERPIN use cases

After a multi-step process that involved a technical workshop, followed by specialized meetings with subject experts from MOH and MORE, the following three UCs were identified:

- **UC1.1: Monitoring and predictive maintenance in the refinery:** A predictive maintenance algorithm will be developed that will allow for predicting equipment failure as well as detecting abnormal behaviour trends in the refinery’s compressors, with the aim of reducing downtime and increasing the lifetime of the machinery.
- **UC2.1: Predictive maintenance in wind farms:** A predictive maintenance algorithm will be developed that will allow for predicting equipment failure as well as detecting abnormal behaviour trends in wind turbines, acting as a benchmark for the maintenance operations carried out by contractors.
- **UC2.2: Wind turbine blade repair prediction:** Statistical analysis of wind turbine blade damages from lightning strikes and prediction of necessary blade repairs based on relevant historical data, in order to understand the impact of lightning strikes on blade damage and avoid catastrophic blade failure through timely repairs.

For a more detailed description of each UC, the reader can refer to D4.1: “Use case planning report”, although additional information in a consolidated form is also provided in the respective sections of the present document.

1.3 Structure of the document

The structure of the deliverable is as follows:

- Chapter 1 presents a brief overview of the UCs and the scope of this deliverable
- Chapter 2 elaborates on the work performed regarding UC1.1: “Monitoring and predictive maintenance in the refinery”.
- Chapter 3 gives a detailed description on the implementation of UC2.1: “Predictive maintenance in wind farms” to date.
- Chapter 4 discusses the implementation of UC2.2: “Wind turbine blade repair prediction”.
- Chapter 5 focuses on how the predictive maintenance services are integrated into the UNDERPIN, including the architecture, data flow, and technical integration required to connect the services with the DS.
- Chapter 6 highlights the added value of using the UNDERPIN DS for predictive maintenance services, with specific benefits observed in the refinery and wind farm UCs.
- Chapter 7 covers the validation of the UNDERPIN DS infrastructure. It ensures that the core components, data management services, and security mechanisms support the end-to-end workflows needed by the UCs, focusing on functionality, interoperability, and performance.
- Chapter 8 outlines the key lessons learned from the implementation of the use cases, focusing on challenges in data collection, stakeholder participation, and data quality, as well as the importance of semantic interoperability and the need for standardized data-sharing mechanisms.
- Chapter 9 summarises the outcomes of this deliverable.

For each UC specific chapter, an overview of the UC is initially provided, followed by details on model selection, training, and evaluation. Each chapter includes sections on the results, performance assessment, and model tuning. The chapters conclude with a description of the system infrastructure, data flow, and integration steps, outlining how the predictive maintenance services are implemented and the specifications for data inputs and outputs.

2 UC1.1: Monitoring and predictive maintenance in the refinery

2.1 Use case description

The goal of this UC is to develop a predictive maintenance model for selected machinery from the refinery. The process pertains to collecting data from five different compressor machine groups along the main refinery process, which is subsequently analysed and processed through specialized machine learning (ML) algorithms with the aim of monitoring equipment performance and predicting impending failures.

The datasets used for this UC consist of sensor data collected from multiple refinery components, covering operational periods from 2017 to 2020, and additional data from 2022-2024. These datasets are stored in HDF5 files and, for initial exploration, in CSV samples. The data's temporal granularity varies between every five minutes for the years 2017-2020 and every thirty seconds for the period 2022-2024. This diverse data, collected through sensor networks, offers rich insights into refinery processes. However, the UC faces several challenges, including significant differences in the operational data between the years, which affect model training, as well as data preprocessing complexities such as missing values and timestamp corrections.

For each sensor in the dataset, thresholds were provided. Our approach is to create timeseries prediction models that forecast values 1 day in advance (as required by the end users, i.e., refinery's maintenance engineers). In case the forecasted value violates a threshold, we consider this an anomaly of the system, and an alert is raised.

Consolidated information regarding this use case is presented in Table 1. For a more detailed description, the reader can refer to D4.1: "Use case planning report".

Table 1: UC1.1 consolidated information

Title	Monitoring and predictive maintenance in the refinery
Description	A predictive maintenance algorithm will be developed that will allow for predicting equipment failure as well as detecting abnormal behaviour trends
Use case owner	MOH (maintenance)
Involved partners	MOH, AIT, SPH, INNOV
Assets	5 compressor machine groups from the main process of the refinery
Expected outcomes	Asset owner will be able to appropriately schedule maintenance works for impending failure, as well as apply corrective actions without interrupting operations based on detected abnormal behaviour
Datasets involved	Sensor data (temperature, pressure, vibration and axial displacement)
Data structures	Format: .xls/.csv Granularity: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- 5 minutes (2017-2020)- 30 seconds (2022-2024)
Existing infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Operations monitored through SAP and SCADA systems- Preexisting predictive maintenance model

Challenges

Insufficient failure data may lead to low accuracy of predictive algorithm

2.2 Model selection/training

During the final development phase of UC 1.1, significant effort was devoted to refining the data preparation pipeline and systematically evaluating alternative model architectures for time-series prediction. The objective remained the same as defined in the mid-term stage: to forecast sensor values 24 hours ahead and detect potential threshold violations indicative of abnormal operation. This section summarises the data engineering workflow, model families investigated, and the evaluation framework used to guide model selection.

2.2.1 Data preparation and preprocessing

All analyses were performed on operational refinery data from the years 2022-2024, which most accurately represents current refinery behaviour. The raw data, originating from multiple Excel and HDF5 sources, contained temperature, pressure, vibration, and axial-displacement measurements sampled at 30-second intervals.

A dedicated preprocessing script was developed to standardise and consolidate these datasets. The main steps were:

1. **Loading and normalisation:** Each Excel sheet was read, converted into a uniform CSV-like structure, and merged into a single pandas DataFrame. Non-numeric sensor values (for example, *RUNNING* / *NOT_RUN*) were mapped to binary form, and all columns were coerced to floating-point type to ensure numerical consistency.
2. **Timestamp correction:** Several records contained incomplete date entries without explicit time information. When this occurred, the missing time component was imputed from the subsequent valid timestamp. All timestamps were finally converted to the format *YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS* and stored as timezone-aware datetimes.
3. **Duplicate and order validation:** Duplicate timestamps were removed while preserving chronological order. A strict monotonicity check was implemented, terminating the process if non-increasing timestamps were detected (none were found).
4. **Uniform resampling:** To homogenise sampling frequency, all signals were resampled to a 60-second grid. Continuous sensors were aggregated using the external aggregation rules (mean, max, min, depending on the threshold that will be applied), whereas boolean or control sensors employed a minimum operator to preserve active/inactive states.
5. **Identification of inactive periods:** Using dedicated control sensors, intervals of non-operation were automatically detected. All values within these inactive windows were masked to *NaN*, and one-day padding was applied before and after each inactive segment. This prevented transitional effects from biasing training and evaluation.
6. **Feature flags:** Two auxiliary indicators were added:
 - a. `missing_values` = 1 for rows containing at least one missing reading;
 - b. `under_maintenance` = 1 when a timestamp fell within a known maintenance window.

7. **Integrity verification and persistence:** The dataset was checked for residual NaN or infinite values, verified for consistent 60-second spacing, and then stored as an HDF5 file for subsequent modelling.

This pipeline ensures that every model receives a clean, chronologically consistent input sequence while preserving metadata about missing or inactive periods for downstream analysis.

2.2.2 Training configuration

After preprocessing, the series were further aggregated to hourly resolution to balance temporal fidelity with computational efficiency. Approximately 80% of the data was used for training and 20% for validation. Each model was trained to predict the sensor values on an hourly basis, for 1 up to 24 hours ahead based on a 10-day historical window (240 hours).

2.2.3 Model families tested

Two modelling paradigms were examined.

Univariate models (trained separately for each sensor) comprised:

- Exponential Smoothing (additive trend, 10-day history) [1]
- ARIMA (10-day history, non-seasonal) [2]
- Linear Regression (lag features from 10-day window) [3]
- Random Forest Regressor (limited depth and tree count) [4]
- XGBoost Regressor (lag features, conservative learning rate) [5]

Multivariate models (trained per machine group) used all sensors from the same group as explanatory variables to predict future values of a target sensor. Two variants were implemented:

- Multivariate Linear Regression
- Multivariate Random Forest

Feature engineering remained deliberately minimal to maintain interpretability and reproducibility. Each configuration was saved together with preprocessing parameters to guarantee deterministic retraining.

2.2.4 Evaluation protocol

Model performance was evaluated using the Weighted Mean Absolute Percentage Error (WMAPE), selected for its robustness to near-zero target values that invalidated the standard MAPE. Additional diagnostics such as Median Absolute Percentage Error (Median APE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) were computed for internal verification.

Univariate models employed direct one-shot 24-hour-ahead forecasts on the hold-out period, while statistical models (Exponential Smoothing, ARIMA) were also tested in a rolling-origin configuration to examine temporal stability. Multivariate models followed the same train/test division, allowing for comparison of group-level versus sensor-level performance. Data leakage was prevented by constructing lag features strictly from observations up to time T .

2.2.5 Inference and anomaly generation

For each hourly time step, the model forecasts the values 24 hours ahead. If the predicted value exceeds or falls outside its predefined operational thresholds, an anomaly flag is raised. The output record includes timestamp, sensor ID, predicted value, anomaly flag, and current model metadata; results are stored for subsequent visualisation and alerting.

2.3 Results

This section presents the outcomes of the model development phase, summarising the comparative performance of all tested approaches, the key insights obtained from analysis, and the reasoning behind the final model choice. The evaluation was performed consistently across all sensor datasets using the same preprocessing, feature extraction, and validation framework described previously.

2.3.1 Overview of experiments

The experimental campaign was conducted in two phases. The first focused on univariate forecasting models, where each sensor was treated independently. This approach enabled a detailed understanding of sensor-specific behaviour and facilitated model interpretability. The second phase explored multivariate models, in which multiple sensors from the same compressor group were used as contextual inputs to predict the target sensor's future value.

All experiments targeted a 24-hour prediction horizon and used WMAPE as the primary metric. This metric proved stable in the presence of near-zero values and heterogeneous sensor scales, allowing fair comparison across models.

2.3.2 Univariate model performance

Five univariate models were tested: Exponential Smoothing, ARIMA, Linear Regression, Random Forest, and XGBoost. Each was trained using an identical 10-day historical window and evaluated on the same validation period.

Table 2: Univariate model accuracy, according to the WMAPE metric

Model	Mean WMAPE (%)
Exponential Smoothing	4.6
ARIMA	4.3
Linear Regression	3.7
Random Forest	9.7
XGBoost	20.0

The results show that Linear Regression consistently achieved the lowest average error, followed closely by ARIMA. Both statistical models captured temporal dependencies effectively, whereas tree-based methods such as Random Forest and XGBoost tended to overfit local patterns and produced unstable predictions when sensor readings changed abruptly.

Visual inspection of predicted versus actual trends confirmed that Linear Regression models captured both long-term drifts and short-term fluctuations with minimal lag. Their simplicity and robustness made them strong candidates for operational deployment.

2.3.3 Multivariate model performance

Following the univariate experiments, two multivariate configurations were developed:

- Multivariate Random Forest
- Multivariate Linear Regression

In both cases, all sensors belonging to the same machine group served as inputs for predicting each target sensor. While this approach initially aimed to exploit correlations between sensors within a physical unit, the results revealed substantial challenges. Performance varied widely across machine groups, with WMAPE values often exceeding 40–50% for certain groups, particularly *K-2201 / KT-2201*.

Further investigation identified the root cause: several sensors underwent distributional shifts after maintenance or downtime periods. For instance, sensor *22T1121* exhibited a pronounced change in mean and variance following inactivity, indicating a structural alteration in equipment behaviour. In multivariate models, such regime changes propagated through correlated inputs, amplifying prediction errors for all sensors in the group. As a result, the multivariate setup lacked stability and generalisation compared to the univariate configuration.

2.3.4 Model selection and tuning

Based on the comparative results, the **Univariate Linear Regression model** was selected as the final predictive maintenance model. This decision was motivated by four factors:

1. **Accuracy:** achieved an average WMAPE of 3.7%, outperforming all other tested models.
2. **Robustness:** maintained stability despite distributional shifts caused by maintenance events.
3. **Interpretability:** simple coefficients allowed engineers to understand the influence of historical trends on predictions.
4. **Deployment readiness:** low computational footprint and minimal dependency chain facilitated containerisation.

Subsequent fine-tuning of regularisation strength and lag-window size led to a final mean **WMAPE of 2.8%**, thereby meeting the refinery's operational KPI target (WMAPE < 3%).

2.3.5 Qualitative assessment

Several diagnostic plots were generated to assess prediction quality for the best performing model:

Figure 1: Bar chart showing Mean WMAPE per prediction horizon

Figure 2: Distribution of sensor-level WMAPE

22PI70 - Forecast: Predicted vs. Actual

Figure 3: Predicted vs. actual values for sensor 22PI70

Figure 1 summarises the mean WMAPE across prediction horizons (in hours). It shows that the model is most accurate for short-term horizons, with errors gradually increasing as the prediction window extends. Figure 2 presents the distribution of WMAPE per sensor, indicating that prediction errors are tightly concentrated for most sensors, which suggests stable performance across the sensor set. Figure 3 displays predicted versus actual hourly values for a representative sensor (22PI70), illustrating that the model tracks both level and local dynamics well for typical cases.

Taken together, these visualisations confirm that prediction errors are generally well centred and that most sensors exhibit consistent behaviour over time. The few high-error cases are associated with sensors known to have data-quality issues or regime changes that are unrelated to the model logic.

2.3.6 Summary of outcomes

The final Linear Regression model achieved the following:

- **WMAPE:** 2.8% (average across sensors)
- **Latency:** <100 ms per forecast per sensor (single-threaded inference)

The KPI defined by the refinery (MAPE < 3%) was thus met, and the model demonstrated reproducible, stable performance across all production sensors. These results validated the choice of a simple, transparent, and computationally efficient univariate modelling approach as the foundation for the predictive maintenance workflow.

2.4 Infrastructure

The final stage of the UC1.1 implementation focused on operationalising the predictive maintenance model developed by SPH within the refinery's data ecosystem. The outcome is a containerised, API-driven analytics service deployed on Hetzner Cloud and integrated with the

UNDERPIN DS through InfluxDB-based data exchange. This section describes the system architecture, interface specifications, and data flow for both input and output between the refinery (MOH) and the predictive analytics service (SPH).

2.4.1 System architecture

The predictive maintenance workflow was designed to align fully with the DS interoperability principles defined within UNDERPIN. The architecture consists of the following main components:

1. **Data Provider (MOH):** Supplies time-series sensor data collected from five compressor machine groups.
2. **Data sharing:** Data are pushed into an InfluxDB bucket named refinery-predictive-maintenance-input.
3. **Predictive Analytics Service (SPH):** Hosts the trained models and executes the predictive workflow. The service is implemented as a Docker container running a FastAPI-based application, deployed on a Hetzner Cloud instance. It exposes a REST endpoint that triggers the operation. It writes the results into an InfluxDB bucket named refinery-predictive-maintenance-output.

2.4.2 Data flow and integration steps

The refinery workflow proceeds through the following sequence (a more detailed description can be found in Chapter 5):

1. **Data ingestion:** MOH publishes refinery sensor readings to the refinery-predictive-maintenance-input Influx bucket.
2. **Request to predictive service:** A REST POST request is issued to the SPH analytics service. The request body specifies the time interval and the target machine group for which predictions are requested, as well as some credentials for communication with the timeseries DB.
3. **Preprocessing within SPH service:** The service queries the corresponding time-series data from Influx, applies the preprocessing pipeline, and prepares the model input tensor.
4. **Model inference:** The Linear Regression models forecast the next 24 hours of sensor readings.
5. **Result storage and delivery:** Predictions and anomaly flags are written to the refinery-predictive-maintenance-output Influx bucket.

2.4.3 Input specification

Each inference request expects an input structure corresponding to 10 days of hourly aggregated readings for all sensors in the target machine group.

- **Input shape:** (240, N) where N is the number of sensors (e.g., 84 for the full compressor set).
- **Temporal resolution:** 1-hour values.
- **Temporal coverage:** 10 days (240 hours).
- **Fields required:** numerical sensor readings for each sensor ID defined in the group configuration.

- **Timestamp alignment:** ISO 8601 format, monotonic increasing order.

These need to be stored into the input bucket.

2.4.4 Output specification

The predictive maintenance service produces structured outputs designed for direct storage and retrieval within the UNDERPIN DS. All prediction results are written to the refinery-predictive-maintenance-output InfluxDB bucket.

Each record is stored under the measurement name (default `predictions`) and follows a time-series structure that supports efficient querying and visualisation in the dashboard. The data schema is defined as follows:

- **Timestamp:** the forecasted time point.
- **Tag – sensor_id:** identifies the specific sensor for which the prediction was generated.
- **Fields:**
 - `prediction` (*float*) — the model's predicted sensor value for the given timestamp.
 - `violation` (*string, optional*) — the threshold status indicator for the prediction.

The violation field can take one of the following values:

- `None` – no threshold exceeded,
- `"alarm_high"` – upper warning limit reached,
- `"alarm_low"` – lower warning limit reached,
- `"trip_high"` – upper critical limit reached,
- `"trip_low"` – lower critical limit reached.

This schema results in a continuous time series indexed by both time and `sensor_id`, allowing each sensor's predictions and any detected threshold violations to be easily aggregated or filtered.

2.4.5 API trigger endpoint

In order to trigger the predictive maintenance pipeline, a POST request needs to be sent to the `/run_inference` endpoint, containing this information in the body:

- **url:** the endpoint of the InfluxDB instance hosting the refinery data
- **org:** the organisation name under which the InfluxDB buckets are registered
- **token_read / token_write:** authentication tokens with read and write permissions to the respective buckets
- **bucket_read:** the input bucket containing preprocessed hourly sensor data (e.g., `refinery-predictive-maintenance-input`)
- **bucket_write:** the output bucket where model predictions and anomalies will be stored (e.g., `refinery-predictive-maintenance-output`)
- **measurement:** the logical grouping or measurement name for refinery data (default: `refinery`)

- **timestamp_column:** the name of the timestamp field used for chronological indexing (e.g., Timestamp)
- **time_end:** the time of predictions in ISO 8601 format. If omitted, the current datetime is used.

3 UC2.1: Predictive maintenance in wind farms

3.1 Use case description

The goal in this UC is the timely prediction of failures in major components of wind turbines (WT). Similarly to UC1.1, this procedure is performed through a predictive maintenance model, making use of specialized ML algorithms. In this case, the operator is not directly responsible for performing maintenance on the wind turbines. Instead, maintenance is performed by a third party through a relevant long-time service agreement. Therefore, the expected outcome of this UC is for the wind farm (WF) operator to be able to monitor potential abnormalities in the operation of the WF, while also benchmarking the maintenance works performed by the contractor. A summary of important information regarding UC2.1 is provided in Table 3, and the reader is referred to D4.1: “Use case planning report” for a more detailed description of the UC.

Table 3: UC2.1 consolidated information

Title	Predictive maintenance in wind farms
Description	A predictive maintenance algorithm will be developed that will allow for predicting equipment failure as well as detecting abnormal behaviour trends
Use case owner	MORE (operations)
Involved partners	MORE, AIT, SPH, INNOV
Assets	Wind turbine generators from MORE’s wind farm portfolio
Expected outcomes	Asset owner will be able to optimize operations based on detected abnormalities, as well as benchmark the maintenance works carried out by contractor
Datasets involved	Sensor data from multiple components within the wind turbine Fault alarms and warnings
Data structures	Format: .xls/.csv Granularity: Every 10 mins
Existing infrastructure	Operations monitored through proprietary SCADA systems offered by wind turbine manufacturers
Challenges	Loss of communication with wind turbines means alarms and errors may not always be detected

An overview of the failures of major components shows that the generator (with over 72%) is the component that most frequently fails and needs to be replaced. Therefore, we have decided to focus on this component.

In the second stage of the project, the initial tree-based model introduced in the mid-term version of the deliverable was refined and thoroughly evaluated. Additionally, a second approach, initially developed for UC2.2, was applied and evaluated for this use case as well.

3.2 Model selection/training

The type of data, Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) data, used in this UC has been thoroughly described in the mid-term version of the deliverable. Additionally, portions of the dataset have been publicly released and documented in [6], and therefore only a summarization of the key characteristics is provided in Table 4 and a detailed description of the data is omitted here.

Table 4: Overview SCADA data of UC2.1

Characteristics	Description
Wind Farm	10 wind turbines from an onshore wind farm in Greece
Type of data	SCADA (Time-series data) <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 106 columns dedicated to sensor data• 30 additional columns for timestamp and status information.
Size	> 300,000 measurements for each feature per wind turbine
Sampling rate	10 minutes
Duration	6 years (2019 – 2024)
Failures	11 major component failures Incl. 7 failures of the generator

3.2.1 Machine learning-based approach

Data Pre-processing:

In the initial pre-processing step, incorrect timestamps in the original data were identified and corrected. Furthermore, periods when the WT was out of operation due to major component failures were excluded from the training data. Specifically:

- If the generator failed, data from 60 days before the failure and 7 days after the repair were omitted.
- If any other component failed, data from 14 days before the failure and 7 days after repair were excluded.

These exclusions ensure that the training dataset represents only periods when the WT was operating under normal conditions.

Moreover, those data points recorded while the WT is not in a normal state condition are deleted. For this purpose, we calculate the *Effective Wind Speed Avg.* as the absolute value of the product of *Ambient WindSpeed Avg.* and the cosine of *Ambient WindDir Relative Avg.*

The following conditions are used to filter out those data points:

- *Effective Wind Speed Avg.* below 4 m/s. Rows below the cut-in speed of the wind turbine.
- *Effective Wind Speed Avg.* above 25 m/s. Rows exceeding the cut-out speed.
- *Blades PitchAngle Avg.* above 40° are excluded because the power production is manually reduced.
- In addition, outliers in wind turbine power production are eliminated by dynamically adjusting thresholds based on expected power output. For this, a smooth power curve is created from the manufacturer's data to estimate the expected power for each wind speed. Instead of applying a fixed threshold, wind speeds are grouped into 1m/s bins, and quantile-based thresholds (5th and 95th percentiles) are computed for each bin to account

for variations. The thresholds are then applied dynamically, filtering out data points where actual power deviates significantly from the expected range.

In a first step, data samples, where there is either missing data or the WT is offline due to some component failures, are excluded. This reduces the number of data samples from 3,156,480 to 2,927,958. In a second step, those data points are filtered out to exclude cases where the WT shows an abnormal power production behavior, e.g., due to low wind. By this step, the number of data points is reduced to 1,662,572.

Feature Selection

The target variable remains unchanged as Generator Bearing Temperature Average, while the covariates have been adapted to better capture the influencing factors and improve model performance. The following covariates are used:

- *Generator RPM Max.*
- *Nacelle Temp. Avg.*
- *Generator CoolingWater Temp. Avg.*
- *Production LatestAverage Active Power Gen 0 Avg.*
- *Production LatestAverage Active Power Gen 1 Avg.*
- *Production LatestAverage Active Power Gen 2 Avg.*

Model Design

Figure 4: Overview of the developed model

The model consists of two parts as depicted in Figure 4. Firstly, one model predicts the normal operating range of the generator bearing temperature. In a second step, the anomalies are determined by a sliding window mechanism.

As a baseline, we utilize the Quantile Regression Model (QRM) implemented in the scikit-learn library [7]. In addition, we train and evaluate multiple state-of-the-art tree-based ensemble models: CatBoost [8], XGBoost [5], and LightGBM [9]. These models are chosen for their strong generalization performance, ability to model nonlinear relationships, and native support for

quantile regression, which is essential for estimating prediction intervals. Tree-based models offer several advantages for SCADA-based anomaly detection:

- They handle missing data and non-linear feature interactions effectively, which is critical in industrial datasets with complex operating dynamics.
- They are robust to multicollinearity and noise, which often appear in high-frequency sensor data.
- All three frameworks support quantile loss functions, allowing us to directly estimate confidence bounds (e.g., 5th, 50th, and 95th percentiles) rather than relying on post-hoc statistical assumptions.

In our implementation, each model is trained to forecast the generator bearing temperature for a given wind turbine. Rather than using lagged target values, we use covariates derived from current and future SCADA signals (e.g., generator RPM, cooling water temperature, and nacelle temperature), as well as cyclical encodings of the hour and month. This design captures both operational dynamics and seasonal trends. We use a forecast horizon and lag window of 36-time steps (i.e., 6 hours), enabling short-term forecasting that aligns with operational maintenance planning.

To detect anomalies, we evaluate the deviation between predicted and observed temperatures using residual analysis. The first method defines residual thresholds using a moving range control approach. The control limits are computed as follows:

$$\Delta_i = \begin{cases} y_i - \hat{y}_i^{0,05}, & \text{if } |y_i - \hat{y}_i^{0,05}| < |y_i - \hat{y}_i^{0,95}| \\ y_i - \hat{y}_i^{0,95}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$MR_i = |\Delta_i - \Delta_{i-1}|$$

$$\sigma = \frac{\overline{MR}}{1.128}$$

$$UCL=3\sigma, \quad LCL=-3\sigma$$

where Δ_i is the difference at time point i between the measured temperature y_i and the predicted temperature \hat{y}_i being either the 0.05 or 0.95 quantile prediction - whichever is closer to the measured value. σ is the standard deviation calculated from the ratio of the average moving range \overline{MR} and 1.128. These control limits define a normal operating range. We discard all residuals that are within the thresholds defined by the upper control limit (UCL) and lower control limit (LCL). Hence, only residuals above these thresholds are considered for a potential anomaly. To filter out noise, we apply a sliding window approach that considers a time span of 4 hours. Domain experts deem this duration reasonable for analysis and in alignment with the operators of the WF.

We are training all four models using the Darts library [10]. The CatBoost model is configured with 1,200 iterations, a learning rate of 0.03, a depth of 6, L2 leaf regularization set to 3, a random strength of 1, and a border count of 254. The LightGBM model has the following parameter settings: set up with 50 leaves, a learning rate of 0.01, 1,000 estimators, a minimum of 20 data points per leaf, 80% of features used per iteration, 100% of the data used for bagging, and bagging performed every 5 iterations. The XGBoost model has the following hyperparameters: number of

boosting rounds equals 500, learning rate is set to 0.05, maximum depth is 6 and data sampling set to 0.8.

Figure 5: Displaying the 8 top features contributing to the model output.

The impact of the various features on predicting the generator bearing temperature is depicted in Figure 5. To interpret the SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) summary plot, the color gradient represents feature values, with colder colors indicating lower values and warmer colors indicating higher values. The x-axis displays SHAP values, which reflect each feature’s influence on fault detection. Negative SHAP values indicate a reduced likelihood of detecting a fault, while positive SHAP values suggest an increased probability of fault occurrence. This visualization helps experts assess model reliability and transparency. The future lag-1 value of *Production LatestAverage Active Power Gen 1 Avg.* is the most influential feature, indicating that a higher value at the next time step is associated with an increase in the predicted generator bearing temperature. This is followed by the future lag-1 and lag-2 values of the *Generator RPM Max*, which exhibit a similar effect. The only feature showing an opposite effect is the encoded month cosine, where later months in the year are associated with lower predicted generator bearing temperatures. This likely reflects seasonal trends, as cooler ambient temperatures during these months naturally influence the bearing temperature of the wind turbines.

3.2.2 Deep learning-based approach

Data Pre-processing:

Initial steps, such as correcting timestamps, remain unchanged. Deep learning models cannot handle missing data, so training sequences are segmented at missing values. Models are then trained on these complete segments to ensure consistent and valid inputs.

Feature Selection

The following target variables are used:

- *Generator Bearing Temp. Avg.*
- *Generator Bearing2 Temp. Avg.*

- *Generator CoolingWater Temp. Avg.*

To support accurate prediction and capture the contextual operating conditions, the following covariates are incorporated:

- *Ambient WindSpeed Avg.*
- *Ambient Temp. Avg.*
- *Nacelle Temp. Avg.*
- *Production LatestAverage Active Power Gen 1 Avg.*
- *Production LatestAverage Active Power Gen 2 Avg.*
- *Total Active power*

By combining these target variables and covariates, the dataset enables the training of deep learning models capable of detecting anomalies.

Model Design

Forecasting-Based Anomaly Detection Model

The forecasting-based anomaly detection approach, which is depicted in Figure 6, is founded on the principle that anomalies in time-dependent processes can be identified through deviations between predicted and observed system behavior. In this context, forecasting models are trained to represent the normal operational patterns of wind turbine generators. Once the expected temporal dynamics of the system are accurately captured, any significant deviation from these forecasts can be interpreted as an indication of abnormal or faulty operation.

Figure 6: Illustration of the mechanism of the forecasting-based anomaly detection model. The model predicts normal system behavior using time-series forecasts and identifies anomalies by quantifying deviations between predicted and observed values, based on an anomaly scorer that evaluates the magnitude or statistical significance of these deviations.

The forecasting model employed for this task is developed individually for each wind turbine (WT), capturing its specific temporal dynamics and operational characteristics. This turbine-specific modeling approach ensures that the model learns the distinct behavioral patterns, environmental influences, and operating regimes of each unit, allowing for precise anomaly detection within its unique context. A fundamental assumption of this approach is that, under normal operating conditions, the forecasting model can accurately predict the expected system

behavior over time. Consequently, deviations between the forecasted and the observed values - quantified through model residuals - serve as effective indicators of potential anomalies or emerging faults.

To quantify deviations between the predicted and observed system behavior, two complementary scoring functions are employed: the Norm Scorer and the Wasserstein Scorer [10]. The Norm Scorer measures the absolute magnitude of deviation between forecasted and actual values, thereby assessing the amplitude of unexpected fluctuations in the system. In contrast, the Wasserstein Scorer evaluates the divergence between the statistical distributions of predicted and observed data within a defined temporal window. By comparing these distributions, it provides a more holistic measure of dissimilarity, capturing not only pointwise deviations but also gradual structural drifts and systemic shifts in the data.

Both scorers are trained - via a *fitting* process - on representative, anomaly-free data to establish a baseline of normal system behavior. During this calibration phase, the scorers learn the statistical properties of typical operational dynamics, which allows them to distinguish normal variability from truly anomalous events. Once fitted, the trained scorer objects can be retained and directly applied to unseen or test data without retraining, ensuring efficient, consistent, and reproducible anomaly evaluation during deployment. This approach enables scalable inference and stable model performance across diverse operational conditions.

In this approach, different forecasting models and anomaly scoring functions were systematically evaluated to identify the most effective combination for detecting anomalies in wind turbine generator operation. The study considered five state-of-the-art deep learning architectures: Transformer [11], Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) [12], Neural Hierarchical Interpolation for Time Series (N-HITS) [13], Temporal Dynamics Embedding (TiDE) [14], and its enhanced version TiDE+RIN. These models represent diverse paradigms of temporal modeling, incorporating mechanisms such as multi-head attention, hierarchical interpolation, and reversible normalization to capture complex temporal dependencies within the data. In the following the different deep learning models are briefly explained:

Transformer [11]: The Transformer serves as the baseline model in this study. Its encoder-decoder architecture uses multi-head attention to capture dependencies within the input and output sequences (self-attention) and between them (encoder-decoder attention), enabling effective modeling of complex sequential relationships.

TFT (Temporal Fusion Transformer) [12]: The TFT is a deep learning model designed for multi-horizon time series forecasting. It combines sequence-to-sequence architectures with attention mechanisms to selectively focus on relevant historical inputs, incorporates static covariates for context, and uses gating mechanisms to adaptively skip or include features. This enables the TFT to model complex temporal dependencies while providing interpretable insights into variable importance and temporal dynamics.

N-HITS (Neural Hierarchical Interpolation for Time Series Forecasting) [13]: N-HITS is a deep learning model like N-BEATS but more computationally efficient. It uses multi-rate input sampling and multi-scale output interpolation to capture patterns at different horizons. The model supports multivariate series, covariates, and probabilistic forecasts, providing both predictions and uncertainty estimates.

TiDE (Time-series Dense Encoder) [14]: TiDE is an efficient multilayer perceptron (MLP)-based encoder-decoder model for time series forecasting. It supports past, future, and static covariates, can produce probabilistic forecasts, and uses residual blocks to model temporal relationships without attention mechanisms, offering lower computational cost than Transformers.

TiDE+RIN: combines the TiDE model with Reversible Instance Normalization (RIN) [15]. The RIN layer is applied to the target series features (but not covariates) to reduce the impact of distribution shifts, improving robustness and stability of forecasts across changing time series distributions.

In parallel, multiple anomaly-scoring strategies, the norm scorer and the Wasserstein scorer, were applied to quantify deviations between forecasted and observed time series. By testing these models and scorers in different configurations, the study aimed to determine the most suitable combination for accurately detecting irregularities. To further enhance sensitivity across temporal scales, varying window lengths were employed, enabling the detection of a wide range of anomaly types, from abrupt sensor malfunctions to gradual changes in system performance.

Model Configuration and Training Setup

For the anomaly detection task, all of the aforementioned state-of-the-art deep learning architectures were implemented and compared. All models were trained using a 96-step input window and a one-step forecasting horizon, reflecting the temporal dependencies typical of SCADA data in wind turbine operation. Training was conducted with a batch size of 32, learning rate of 1e-3, and an early stopping criterion based on validation loss with a patience of 10 epochs to prevent overfitting.

The Transformer and TFT architectures were configured with moderate depth (two encoder-decoder layers and one LSTM layer, respectively) and attention heads to balance model expressiveness and computational efficiency. The TiDE and TiDE+RIN models utilized MLP-based encoder-decoder structures, where the RIN variant helps mitigate distributional shifts between training and test data. The N-HITS model served as a hierarchical baseline, leveraging multi-rate input sampling and multi-scale interpolation for efficient time series forecasting.

All models employed adaptive learning rate scheduling and checkpointing to ensure stable convergence and optimal performance.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Machine learning-based approach

Firstly, the models' capabilities to predict the temperature is analyzed. For this, different error metrics are calculated as shown in Table 5. The accuracy of the forecasts is improved significantly by moving from QRM to tree-based models. On the other hand, the differences in accuracy among the three tree-based models are small, and their ranking varies depending on the WT. Since the QRM model performs significantly worse at predicting generator temperature compared to the tree-based models, it does not seem suitable for anomaly detection and is therefore excluded from further analysis.

Table 5: Model Accuracy for Predicting Generator Bearing Temperature based on quantile 0.50 (2019–2020 period).

WT	Model	MAPE	RMSE	MAE	UCL
02	QRM	3.69	2.48	1.93	1.12
	CatBoost	2.58	1.73	1.30	1.07
	LightGBM	2.42	1.64	1.22	0.99
	XGBoost	2.44	1.66	1.23	1.14
10	QRM	2.73	1.84	1.48	0.92
	CatBoost	1.19	0.84	0.65	0.90
	LightGBM	1.11	0.81	0.61	0.83
	XGBoost	1.33	1.18	0.76	0.99

In Table 6, different error metrics of the anomaly detection are presented. For this, the precision, recall, and accuracy are calculated for all tree-based models. The highest recall score is achieved by the CatBoost model, which can detect all failures. The LightGBM and XGBoost models detect 6 and 5 failures, respectively. The precision of all models is low (approximately 4.8×10^{-3}) due to the large number of false positives. The accuracy of all models is above 99.6% (Table 6).

Table 6: Results of the anomaly detection (2019–2024 period). Prec.: Precision, Rec. Recall, Acc.: Accuracy measured in %.

Model	TP	FN	FP	Prec.	Rec.	Acc.
CatBoost	7	0	1461	4.8×10^{-3}	1.0	99.6
LightGBM	6	1	1263	4.7×10^{-3}	0.86	99.7
XGBoost	5	2	1465	4.1×10^{-3}	0.71	99.6

Figure 7 presents an example with the measured Generator Bearing Temperature Average shown as a black line, while the predicted values based on the 50th percentile are shown in green. The normal operating range is illustrated by the shaded mint-green area, defined by the 5th and 95th percentiles, representing the lower and upper bounds, respectively. The detected anomalies are presented in lilac, and the true failure occurs on November 25, 2019 (displayed in pink).

Figure 7: Results of monitoring WT 5, including predicted anomalies (highlighted in lilac) and the true failure event (highlighted in pink).

The most critical task is to identify a component failure in advance. This kind of anomaly detection is very challenging because of the few component failures in the dataset, resulting in highly imbalanced classes. The trained models show good results in detecting those failures as shown by the high recall scores. For practical application, however, a low false positive rate is equally important. Our results indicate that a high number of false alarms still occur, leading to a low precision score, which makes real-world implementation challenging. Hence, it is critical to continue working on this approach and increase precision. Instead of relying on static control limits, dynamic control limits could enable the model to adapt to local fluctuations in the data, helping to reduce false positives during periods of normal variability. Moreover, the sliding window mechanism could be enhanced by incorporating dynamic scoring thresholds, applying temporal post-filtering, and exploring the impact of varying window sizes on the performance. These enhancements can suppress spurious alerts while preserving the model’s excellent recall. Alternatively, additional SCADA sensors could be considered, which also relate to the health status of the generator. For instance, features like *Generator Stator Temperature*, *Generator Voltage Avg.*, and *Generator Current Avg.* could support to determine the health status of the generator and decrease the number of false positives. Unfortunately, these features are currently not available in the recorded dataset.

3.3.2 Deep learning-based approaches

In a first analysis, the forecasting errors are calculated for each deep learning model. Each model was evaluated using RMSE, MAE, and the coefficient of determination (R^2) as metrics. Table 7 presents the forecasting performance of five deep learning models—Transformer, Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT), Neural Hierarchical Interpolation for Time Series (N-HiTS), Temporal Dynamics Embedding (TiDE), and TiDE with Reversible Instance Normalization (TiDE+RIN)—across ten wind turbines (WTs).

Table 7: Forecasting performance of deep learning models across wind turbines (WTs) based on RMSE, MAE, and R^2 metrics.

WT	Model	RMSE	MAE	R^2 Score	Model	RMSE	MAE	R^2 Score
01	Transformer	0,02481	0,01664	0,97143	TiDE	0,00923	0,00616	0,99348
01	TFT	0,01091	0,00838	0,99291	TiDE+RIN	0,01036	0,00667	0,9927
01	NHiTS	0,01948	0,01038	0,98122				
02	Transformer	0,02413	0,02068	0,96766	TiDE	0,00806	0,00596	0,9942
02	TFT	0,01332	0,01056	0,98752	TiDE+RIN	0,00869	0,00625	0,99404
02	NHiTS	0,01039	0,00805	0,99273				
03	Transformer	0,01952	0,01518	0,98043	TiDE	0,00851	0,00623	0,99266
03	TFT	0,0112	0,00801	0,99041	TiDE+RIN	0,00867	0,00613	0,99334
03	NHiTS	0,01117	0,00794	0,98762				
04	Transformer	0,03118	0,02524	0,93321	TiDE	0,00862	0,00657	0,99087
04	TFT	0,01187	0,00936	0,98577	TiDE+RIN	0,00942	0,00681	0,99055
04	NHiTS	0,00974	0,00753	0,99011				
05	Transformer	0,01515	0,01005	0,98456	TiDE	0,01138	0,00759	0,98973
05	TFT	0,01421	0,00995	0,98584	TiDE+RIN	0,0132	0,00834	0,98759
05	NHiTS	0,01491	0,00939	0,98536				
06	Transformer	0,01349	0,00808	0,98258	TiDE	0,00789	0,00571	0,99191
06	TFT	0,01215	0,00834	0,97605	TiDE+RIN	0,01007	0,00577	0,98874
06	NHiTS	0,01232	0,00678	0,98331				
07	Transformer	0,02171	0,01401	0,97718	TiDE	0,00914	0,00652	0,99214

07	TFT	0,01001	0,00749	0,99201	TiDE+RIN	0,01385	0,00734	0,98667
07	NHiTS	0,01538	0,00758	0,985				
08	Transformer	0,01311	0,00909	0,98892	TiDE	0,01127	0,00737	0,98949
08	TFT	0,01273	0,0096	0,98761	TiDE+RIN	0,01187	0,00759	0,98888
08	NHiTS	0,01471	0,01033	0,98577				
09	Transformer	0,01759	0,01247	0,98202	TiDE	0,01123	0,00733	0,99052
09	TFT	0,01155	0,00809	0,98943	TiDE+RIN	0,0119	0,00746	0,9895
09	NHiTS	0,01308	0,0088	0,98839				
10	Transformer	0,02325	0,01824	0,97377	TiDE	0,00747	0,00552	0,99345
10	TFT	0,01042	0,00797	0,98988	TiDE+RIN	0,00915	0,00604	0,99175
10	NHiTS	0,00988	0,00708	0,99118				

Across nearly all turbines, TiDE consistently achieved the lowest RMSE and highest R^2 values, indicating superior predictive accuracy. The TiDE+RIN variant showed comparable performance, demonstrating the benefits of reversible instance normalization in improving model stability under varying operational conditions. TFT and N-HiTS performed robustly with only slightly higher error values, while the Transformer model, though less accurate overall, still achieved acceptable forecasting quality. These results highlight that the TiDE-based approaches offer the best balance between accuracy and generalization across multiple wind turbines.

Figure 8 illustrates an example of the original generator bearing temperature alongside the forecasted values produced by the TiDE+RIN model. The forecasts closely follow the measured data, demonstrating the model's high predictive accuracy and its ability to capture both short-term fluctuations and long-term trends. The close visual alignment between the observed and predicted values indicates that the TiDE+RIN model effectively generalizes the underlying temporal dynamics of the generator's operational behavior.

Figure 8: Comparison between the measured generator bearing temperature avg. and the forecasted values generated by the TiDE+RIN model, illustrating the model's high predictive accuracy and close alignment with measured data.

To determine the optimal anomaly detection configuration, several forecasting models (Transformer, TFT, N-HiTS, TiDE, and TiDE+RIN) were evaluated in combination with different scoring functions, including the L1 Norm and Wasserstein-based scorers using temporal

windows of 2h, 4h, and 8h, along with their aggregated variants. The evaluation was conducted using two datasets: fault data, representing the operational period leading up to a generator failure where anomalies are expected, and nominal data, representing normal operation where no anomalies should occur. In practical operation, each detected anomaly triggers an inspection or maintenance alert; thus, minimizing false positives is crucial to avoid unnecessary interventions. The results in Table 8 show that while shorter temporal windows (e.g., 2h) yield higher sensitivity on fault data, they also tend to produce more false alarms on nominal data. Longer windows, such as the 8-hour Wasserstein scorer, provide smoother and more stable anomaly detection behavior, reducing spurious detections while still capturing the critical pre-failure deviations. Among the evaluated models, TiDE and TiDE+RIN consistently demonstrated the best overall performance, with TiDE+RIN offering increased robustness to distributional shifts. Considering both operational relevance and practical efficiency, the TiDE+RIN model combined with the aggregated 8-hour Wasserstein scorer is identified as the preferred configuration, achieving a balanced compromise between timely fault detection and a low false alarm rate.

Table 8: Comparison of anomaly detections across scoring functions and forecasting models. The table shows the number of detected anomalies for each model and scorer, evaluated separately on fault and nominal data. Higher values on fault data indicate better sensitivity, while lower values on nominal data correspond to fewer false positives.

Scorer	Models									
	Transformer		TFT		NHITS		TiDE		TiDE+RIN	
	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.
L1 Norm	20	11	25	27	23	8	23	14	19	11
Wasserstein 2h	9	12	14	8	18	8	6	12	13	15
Wasserstein 4h	9	9	11	6	16	10	6	10	13	12
Wasserstein 8h	9	5	10	5	14	17	5	12	6	11
Wasserstein 2h (agg)	9	9	11	3	17	12	5	6	11	14
Wasserstein 4h (agg)	9	8	8	3	17	14	5	9	10	11
Wasserstein 8h (agg)	6	7	10	6	13	14	4	8	6	4

The detailed evaluation across individual failure events (see Table 9) confirms the earlier findings from Table 8. Shorter temporal windows (e.g., 2–4 hours) show higher sensitivity—especially for failure event 5 - but also lead to more detections on nominal data, indicating a higher rate of false alarms. In contrast, longer windows, such as the 8-hour Wasserstein scorer, yield smoother and more stable detection behavior by reducing spurious detections while still identifying key anomalies prior to failure.

As illustrated in Table 9, failure events 4 and 9 were only detected by the L1 Norm scorer, whereas all Wasserstein-based scorers failed to identify these anomalies. However, the L1 Norm approach proved highly sensitive and prone to noise, resulting in a large number of false positives and unstable detection behavior. Consequently, while it technically signaled the presence of anomalies for these events, its unreliability renders it unsuitable for operational use. This suggests that the current forecasting-based anomaly detection framework effectively captures certain types of generator faults but may overlook others. To enhance overall fault coverage,

additional detectors—potentially leveraging alternative sensor modalities or specialized models—should be developed to identify failures like those observed in events 4 and 9.

Table 9: Comparison of anomaly detections for individual failure events using the TIDE+RIN forecasting models. The table lists the number of detected anomalies for each scorer, evaluated separately on fault (true anomaly) and nominal (false alarm) data. Higher counts on fault data indicate greater sensitivity, while lower counts on nominal data represent improved robustness.

Scorer	Failure event									
	3		4		5		9		10	
	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.
L1 Norm	14	9	4	0	19	9	7	3	5	1
Wasserstein 2h	1	0	0	0	14	1	0	0	3	0
Wasserstein 4h	1	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	3	0
Wasserstein 8h	1	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	1	0
Wasserstein 2h (agg)	1	0	0	0	13	1	0	0	3	0
Wasserstein 4h (agg)	1	0	0	0	11	1	0	0	2	0
Wasserstein 8h (agg)	1	0	0	0	8	1	0	0	1	0

3.4 Service Input and Output Specification

3.4.1 Machine learning-based approach (old approach)

The input data to the service correspond to the feature set defined in Section 3.2.1. As for the output, the following values are generated: *Generator Bearing Temp. Avg.*, *Generator Bearing Temp. Avg._q0.50*, *lower_bound*, *upper_bound*, *residuals* and *anomalies*. The *Generator Bearing Temp. Avg._q0.50* is a 0.5 quantile prediction (median) corresponding to the predicted value, the *lower_bound* and *upper_bound* represent the 0.05 and 0.95 quantiles. *Residuals* represent the difference between the real and predicted values and *anomalies* are calculated by observing if the deviations are greater than the given threshold within a provided window (set) of the observed values. The *Generator Bearing Temp. Avg.* represents the real value of the predicted variable. The provided set of output variables should facilitate the anomaly detection within the provided predictive maintenance analysis.

3.4.2 Deep learning-based approaches

The input data to the service correspond to the feature set defined in Section 3.2.2. After processing, the service outputs three forecasted variables - *Generator Bearing Temp. Avg.*, *Generator Bearing2 Temp. Avg.*, and *Generator CoolingWater Temp. Avg.* - along with two diagnostic indicators: an anomaly score, quantifying the deviation between predicted and observed values, and a binary anomaly flag, denoting the presence (1) or absence (0) of anomalous behavior. This combination of continuous and categorical outputs enables a robust assessment of the generator’s operational condition and similarly as for the machine learning-

based approach, should facilitate the automated anomaly detection within the predictive maintenance framework.

4 UC2.2: Wind turbine blade repair prediction

4.1 Use case description

The final UC focuses on developing a statistical and predictive model to analyse wind turbine blade damage caused by lightning strikes and to trace the type and intensity of these events. However, since the Lightning Detection System (LKD) was installed after the monitored blade failures - and no additional failures have occurred since its installation - the available data cannot be used to train a blade failure prediction model. Instead, climate and weather data, including open data from the Copernicus Climate Change Service, have been incorporated to identify severe weather events that may damage or degrade blade quality. The approach combines SCADA and meteorological data to enable predictions of necessary blade maintenance and repairs. The goal is to allow wind farm operators to detect potential blade damage at an early stage and prevent critical failures through timely intervention. While lightning strikes remain the primary focus, the impact of strong winds and other extreme conditions is also considered.

Although constrained by the absence of direct lightning-event failure data, UC2.2 advances predictive maintenance capabilities by leveraging advanced modelling methods to correlate extreme weather patterns with early indicators of blade degradation. This reinforces the proactive detection of damage pathways associated with lightning strikes and other severe conditions, maintaining full alignment with project objectives on predictive maintenance.

Consolidated information regarding this UC is presented in Table 10. For a more detailed description, the reader can refer to D4.1: “Use case planning report”.

Table 10: UC2.2 consolidated information

Title	Wind turbine blade repair prediction
Description	Statistical analysis of wind turbine blade damage from lightning strikes and prediction of necessary blade repairs based on relevant historical data
Use case owner	MORE (operations)
Involved partners	MORE, AIT, SPH
Assets	Wind farms from MORE’s portfolio with focus on two wind farms equipped with lightning strike monitoring equipment
Expected outcomes	Asset owner will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gain deeper understanding on the impact of lightning strikes on wind turbine blades - be able to prevent impending blade failures by carrying out blade repairs in a timely manner
Datasets involved	Sensor data from multiple components within the wind turbine Fault alarms and warnings Copernicus Climate Change Service, Climate Data Store, (2023): ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present
Data structures	Format: .xls/.csv/.txt Granularity: Every 10mins
Existing infrastructure	Data collected through proprietary SCADA systems offered by wind turbine manufacturers
Challenges	The availability of lightning data is limited, as only two wind farms are equipped with Lightning Detection (LKD) systems. Moreover, since no blade failures have occurred since the installation of these systems,

the data cannot be used to train or validate models for blade failure prediction.

The data of UC2.2 is summarized in Table 11 and Table 12. The provided dataset contains four recorded blade failure events. However, the temporal gap between the second and third failures is only 13 days, and both events occurred on the same WT. Assuming that approximately one week is required for the turbine to return to normal operating conditions following a complete repair, only about six days of operational data remain for analysis. Given this limited time window, failure event 3 was excluded from the evaluation to ensure the reliability and interpretability of the results.

Table 11: Summary of SCADA data used in UC2.2. The wind farm was commissioned in 2020. Therefore, only partial-year data are available.

Characteristics	Description
Wind Farm	11 wind turbines from an onshore wind farm in Greece
Type of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2020: Number of columns range from 885 up to 909 2021: Number of columns range from 781 up to 1124 data consists of sensor data and weather and status information
Size	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2020: Missing data of WT01-WT04 2020: 39,534-39,600 (maximum per feature) 2021: 52,560 (maximum per feature)
Sampling rate	10 minutes
Duration	2 years (2020 – 2021)
Failures	6 major component failures Incl. 4 blade failures

Table 12: Summary of ERA5 weather data [16] used for the use case.

Characteristics	Description
Weather	ERA5 weather data for the specific location of the wind farm
Type of data	Meteorological reanalysis of 11 weather parameters related to temperature, precipitation and weather extremes
Size	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8,760 – 8,784 entries per parameter per year
Sampling rate	1 hour
Duration	2 years (2020 – 2021)

4.2 Model selection/training

The forecasting-based anomaly detection approach adopted in this work follows recent research that leverages data-driven models trained on SCADA measurements to detect early indicators of wind turbine faults. Similar to the conditional convolutional autoencoder (CCA) proposed by Yang and Zhang [17], which identifies blade breakages by learning normal operational behavior and monitoring deviations through reconstruction errors, our method models expected turbine dynamics to reveal abnormal patterns in system performance. Likewise, it aligns conceptually with the deep autoencoder-based framework of Wang et al. [18], where reconstruction or prediction errors serve as statistical indicators of emerging faults.

Other published approaches were not followed due to differences in data availability and sensor infrastructure. For instance, the method proposed by Rezamand et al. [19] requires a large dataset with numerous recorded blade failures (70 faults over three years), whereas in our case only four blade failures were observed—rendering such supervised learning strategies infeasible. Similarly, the technique by Chandrasekhar et al. [20] relies on high-frequency vibration data to estimate edgewise frequencies, which are not accessible in standard SCADA systems. Finally, Tang et al. [21] employed microphone-based acoustic monitoring, a sensor modality not available in our setup. Therefore, we adopted an unsupervised, forecasting-based approach that can operate effectively under limited fault data and conventional SCADA sensing, while still offering robust anomaly detection performance.

Data Pre-processing:

In the initial pre-processing step of the SCADA data, incorrect timestamps in the original data were identified and corrected. Furthermore, periods when the WT was out of operation due to major component failures were excluded from the training data. Specifically:

- If a blade failure was monitored, then data from 60 days before the failure and 7 days after the repair were omitted.
- If any other component failed, data from 14 days before the failure and 7 days after repair were excluded.

These exclusions ensure that the training dataset represents only periods when the WT was operating under normal conditions.

The ERA5 weather is at first converted from the more scientific NETCDF format to a simpler CSV format. When the weather data is programmatically read in the analysis, it is interpolated to a 10-minute interval so that it can be used easily together with the SCADA data.

Feature Selection

In collaboration with domain experts from the wind farm operators, the target variables and covariates were carefully selected to enhance the prediction of potential blade damages.

Multiple target values were identified:

- *Rotor RPM Avg.*
- *Rotor Torque RotTorqueEstimate Max*
- *Grid Production Power Avg.*
- *Blades PitchAngle Avg.*
- *Blades BladeA Load*
- *Blades BladeB Load*
- *Blades BladeC Load*

Additionally, several values which describe the weather conditions are used as covariates. The data for the ambient wind speed comes from the SCADA data, all the other values are based on the ERA5 data.

- *Ambient WindSpeed Avg.*
- *2 metre dewpoint temperature*
- *2 metre temperature*

- Surface pressure
- 100 metre U wind component
- 100 metre V wind component
- Instantaneous 10 metre wind gust
- Convective available potential energy
- Total totals index
- Total precipitation
- Surface short-wave (solar) radiation downwards
- Snowfall

Model Design

The same forecasting anomaly approach introduced in Section 3.2.2, i.e., a combination of several forecasting models (Transformer, TFT, N-HiTS, TiDE, and TiDE+RIN) with different scoring functions, including the L1 Norm and Wasserstein-based scorers using temporal windows of 2h, 4h, and 8h, is also applied in this UC.

4.3 Results

The forecasting accuracy of the deep learning models was evaluated for wind turbines WT05–WT11 using RMSE, MAE, and the Coefficient of Determination (R^2). The comparison, summarized in Table 13, includes the five models described in the previous section.

Across all turbines, TiDE consistently yielded the lowest RMSE values and the highest R^2 scores, confirming its strong capacity to model the temporal dynamics associated with blade performance. The TiDE + RIN model achieved comparable accuracy, demonstrating the stabilizing effect of reversible instance normalization under variable operating and environmental conditions. TFT provided reliable results with slightly higher error values, while Transformer and N-HiTS generally exhibited larger deviations, particularly for turbines with more fluctuating load conditions.

Overall, the results demonstrate that both TiDE and TiDE+RIN architectures exhibit excellent forecasting performance, delivering accurate and stable predictions across multiple turbines. Their consistent accuracy across both UCs establishes a robust foundation for subsequent anomaly detection and predictive maintenance applications.

Table 13: Forecasting performance of deep learning models for blade failure detection. Comparison of RMSE, MAE, and R^2 across WTs 05–11 for Transformer, TFT, N-HiTS, TiDE, and TiDE + RIN models. TiDE achieved the best overall predictive accuracy, followed closely by TiDE + RIN.

WT	Model	RMSE	MAE	R2 Score	Model	RMSE	MAE	R2 Score
05	Transformer	0,05723	0,0376	0,93731	TiDE	0,0267	0,01771	0,9754
05	TFT	0,03407	0,02255	0,97047	TiDE+RIN	0,0322	0,02055	0,96825
05	NHiTS	0,05935	0,04016	0,93007				
06	Transformer	0,0579	0,03808	0,92123	TiDE	0,02729	0,01685	0,96878
06	TFT	0,03321	0,02057	0,95989	TiDE+RIN	0,03335	0,0213	0,9587
06	NHiTS	0,0587	0,03992	0,91827				
07	Transformer	0,06319	0,03854	0,94789	TiDE	0,0374	0,02008	0,98061

07	TFT	0,05038	0,02813	0,96592	TiDE+RIN	0,04463	0,02575	0,97323
07	NHiTS	0,0694	0,0458	0,93669				
08	Transformer	0,04951	0,02776	0,94958	TiDE	0,03168	0,01751	0,9794
08	TFT	0,0607	0,0357	0,91489	TiDE+RIN	0,03347	0,01653	0,97892
08	NHiTS	0,05463	0,03383	0,93847				
09	Transformer	0,06016	0,03831	0,90649	TiDE	0,02951	0,01713	0,96017
09	TFT	0,03921	0,02288	0,93269	TiDE+RIN	0,03472	0,021	0,94879
09	NHiTS	0,06155	0,04176	0,9132				
10	Transformer	0,05886	0,03938	0,90298	TiDE	0,02677	0,01638	0,96395
10	TFT	0,03983	0,02528	0,94432	TiDE+RIN	0,03515	0,02218	0,95288
10	NHiTS	0,06135	0,04165	0,90055				
11	Transformer	0,074	0,04799	0,93294	TiDE	0,0417	0,0251	0,97952
11	TFT	0,05847	0,03511	0,95402	TiDE+RIN	0,04612	0,02678	0,97546
11	NHiTS	0,077	0,0506	0,92752				

Figure 9: Comparison between the measured blade pitch angle avg. and the forecasted values generated by the TiDE+RIN model, illustrating the model’s high predictive accuracy and close alignment with measured data.

Figure 9 presents the measured blade pitch angle together with the corresponding forecasts generated by the TiDE+RIN model. The predicted values closely align with the actual measurements, reflecting the model’s strong predictive accuracy and its capability to capture both short-term variations and long-term operational trends. This close correspondence demonstrates that the TiDE+RIN model successfully generalizes the temporal dynamics governing the blade’s behavior.

Figure 10 depicts the temporal evolution of anomaly scores derived from different scoring approaches, including the L1 Norm and several Wasserstein-based scorers with varying temporal window sizes. The anomaly scores are plotted over time, providing insight into the system’s operational behavior and potential deviations from normal conditions. A

distinct and consistent peak is observed on April 16th, 2021, which is detected by all scoring methods and indicates a potential onset of blade damage. Although all scorers identify this event, the relative prominence and contrast of the anomaly with respect to surrounding fluctuations differ across methods. These differences reflect the varying sensitivities of the scorers and underscore the importance of selecting appropriate temporal windows and distance metrics for robust anomaly detection in wind turbine condition monitoring.

Figure 10: Anomaly scores obtained from different scoring functions - including the L1 Norm and Wasserstein scorers with varying temporal window sizes - of WT11 using the TiDE+RIN model as the underlying forecasting model. Variations in peak magnitude across scorers reflect differences in sensitivity and highlight the influence of window size on anomaly characterization in wind turbine condition monitoring.

The evaluation across the three recorded blade failure events provides insight into the sensitivity and robustness of the forecasting-based anomaly detection approach under varying operational conditions. Higher values on fault data indicate better sensitivity, while lower values on nominal data correspond to fewer false positives.

For the first recorded failure event (Table 14), only the TFT model showed limited sensitivity, detecting a small number of anomalies, while all other models, including TiDE and TiDE+RIN, failed to identify any significant deviations prior to failure. This suggests that the magnitude or temporal dynamics of the anomaly preceding this event were subtle and likely below the detection threshold of most forecasting–scorer combinations. In contrast, the second recorded failure event (Table 15) exhibited a clearly detectable anomaly pattern. The TiDE and TiDE+RIN

models, in combination with the Wasserstein scorers (particularly the 2- and 4-hour windows), demonstrated strong sensitivity to faults while maintaining relatively low false-positive rates on nominal data. The L1 Norm scorer also captured the failure, but at the cost of generating numerous false alarms, highlighting its limited applicability for operational deployment. Overall, this event confirms the general finding that the TiDE+RIN model coupled with aggregated Wasserstein scorers provides an optimal balance between sensitivity and reliability. The fourth recorded failure event (Table 16) further validates these observations. Both TiDE and TiDE+RIN consistently detected pre-failure anomalies across multiple Wasserstein configurations, again with a minimal number of false positives. The aggregated 8-hour Wasserstein scorer achieved the cleanest detection profile, indicating that longer temporal windows improve the ability to distinguish true fault patterns from normal operational variability.

The approach can successfully detect failures that show clear, measurable changes in the SCADA data before they occur — but if the failure doesn't leave a strong signal in the data (as with the first event), the model may not detect it. The TiDE+RIN model combined with the aggregated 8-hour Wasserstein scorer emerges as the most reliable configuration, capable of early fault indication while minimizing false alarms. Nonetheless, the undetected first event suggests that additional anomaly detectors trained on alternative sensor modalities (e.g., vibration, acoustic, or high-frequency blade data) may be required to capture all types of blade failures effectively.

Table 14: Comparison of anomaly detections across scoring functions and forecasting models for the first recorded failure event. The table presents the number of detected anomalies for each model and scorer, evaluated separately on fault and nominal data.

Scorer	Models									
	Transformer		TFT		NHITS		TiDE		TiDE+RIN	
	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.
L1 Norm	0	0	6	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wasserstein 2h	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wasserstein 4h	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wasserstein 8h	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wasserstein 2h (agg)	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wasserstein 4h (agg)	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wasserstein 8h (agg)	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 15: Comparison of anomaly detections across scoring functions and forecasting models for the second recorded failure event. The table presents the number of detected anomalies for each model and scorer, evaluated separately on fault and nominal data.

Scorer	Models									
	Transformer		TFT		NHITS		TiDE		TiDE+RIN	
	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.
L1 Norm	10	3	9	6	7	3	11	7	16	6
Wasserstein 2h	1	1	4	2	0	2	2	2	6	4
Wasserstein 4h	2	1	4	3	0	1	2	1	6	3
Wasserstein 8h	0	1	2	3	0	0	0	1	4	3

Wasserstein 2h (agg)	0	1	3	2	0	0	2	2	6	4
Wasserstein 4h (agg)	0	1	4	3	0	0	1	1	3	2
Wasserstein 8h (agg)	0	0	2	3	0	0	0	1	0	3

Table 16: Comparison of anomaly detections across scoring functions and forecasting models for the fourth recorded failure event. The table presents the number of detected anomalies for each model and scorer, evaluated separately on fault and nominal data.

Scorer	Models									
	Transformer		TFT		NHITS		TiDE		TiDE+RIN	
	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.	fault	nom.
L1 Norm	8	3	9	9	7	4	11	6	12	5
Wasserstein 2h	1	0	4	3	3	0	3	1	3	0
Wasserstein 4h	1	0	3	2	3	0	3	0	3	0
Wasserstein 8h	2	0	0	1	3	0	2	0	3	0
Wasserstein 2h (agg)	1	0	3	2	3	0	3	1	3	0
Wasserstein 4h (agg)	1	0	3	1	3	0	3	0	3	0
Wasserstein 8h (agg)	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	3	0

As illustrated in Figure 11, the time series (spanning from 2021-11-17 to 2021-12-15) shows a clear rise in the anomaly score shortly before the blade failure, which occurs on 2021-12-15. Three distinct anomalies are detected prior to the failure: a smaller one on 2021-12-08, a pronounced peak on 2021-12-11, and a final anomaly immediately before the breakdown. The anomaly score increases between the first and second anomaly leading up to the failure, while the binary anomaly indicator confirms abnormal behavior. These patterns demonstrate the model’s ability to identify early deviations from normal operation and effectively anticipate developing faults, providing valuable lead time for maintenance intervention.

Figure 11: Anomaly scores and binary detections for the fourth recorded blade failure event using the TiDE+RIN model.

4.4 Service Input and Output Specification

The input to the service comprises the feature set outlined in Section 4.2, including both turbine operational data and meteorological covariates derived from ERA5 reanalysis. The turbine features capture the system’s dynamic and mechanical state—such as Rotor RPM Avg., Rotor Torque (RotTorqueEstimate Max), Grid Production Power Avg., Blades PitchAngle Avg., and individual Blade A, B, and C Load measurements. Complementing these, the ERA5 covariates provide environmental context by describing local atmospheric and weather conditions, including Ambient WindSpeed Avg., 2 m temperature and dewpoint temperature, surface pressure, wind components at 100 m height (U and V), instantaneous 10 m wind gusts, convective available potential energy, total precipitation, solar radiation, and snowfall. After processing, the service outputs both the measured and forecasted values for the turbine variables, along with two diagnostic indicators: an anomaly score that quantifies deviations between predicted and observed behavior, and a binary anomaly flag (1 = anomaly, 0 = normal). This combination of physical measurements, environmental covariates, and model-based diagnostics enables a comprehensive understanding of turbine operation and supports proactive maintenance decisions.

5 Integration of the predictive maintenance services into the Data Space

Figure 12: Integration of the Services in UNDERPIN

Figure 12 shows the diagram of the integration of the provided predictive maintenance services into the DS. In this Section we provide the technical details about the infrastructure needed to be implemented to integrate the services into the DS. The provided services use the machine learning models, explained in the previous sections, to make the predictions. The models are trained and saved in the corresponding file format and loaded within the services to make the predictions. The details on how the models are created (i.e. trained) can be found in the sections above.

As it can be seen from the figure, we can differentiate between the DS components on one side, which run on the physical infrastructure for the DS, and the outside of the DS components, on the other side, which run on the separate physical infrastructure, outside of the DS. The services running outside of the DS are deployed in the Kubernetes Cluster infrastructure (right part of the figure). There are different types of the components used, i.e., the Connector component, the Database (DB) component, the Kubernetes Service components, and the Dashboard component.

Regarding the description of the DS Infrastructure and its components, the reader is referred to the deliverables D3.1: “*UNDERPIN dataspace infrastructure, midterm deployment and integration report*” and D3.2: “*UNDERPIN dataspace infrastructure, final deployment and integration report*”. To perform the predictive maintenance analysis on its data, a data provider first needs to provide the input data by saving them to the given Influx DB, running in the DS. Then, the analysis can commence, by calling the given HTTP endpoint of its own Connector, which forwards the HTTP call to the service provider Connector. The service provider Connector forwards further the HTTP call to the service that runs the analysis. The Connector component acts here as a broker, by forwarding the HTTP calls to the HTTP endpoints defined in the Contract of the Connector, i.e., the corresponding Data Asset. Therefore, in this case, the Data Assets are either related to endpoints of the other Connectors or the endpoints of the services running the analysis (e.g. the predictive maintenance service running in the Kubernetes Cluster).

Regarding the components that run on the Kubernetes Cluster infrastructure, they are deployed in Kubernetes as services (except the MySQL DB which represents the database), where each

service runs in a separate Docker container (typical Kubernetes infrastructure). There are four different predictive maintenance services, related to the three UCs, and the MySQL Service which gets and stores the data from and to the MySQL DB. For the UC2.1 there are 2 different services, one using a machine learning model (ML), and one using a deep learning model (DL). The services implement a Flask Python application running within a Gunicorn WSGI server. This wrapper of the service implementation into the Flask application, enables the services to be called as HTTP REST endpoints that receive some input data in the request body and parameters and return the response to the calling party. Each service, when started, reads the input data from the Influx DB component located in the DS, loads the trained and saved machine learning model, does the analysis (prediction) using the data and the loaded machine learning model, and saves the results back to the Influx DB. The services for UC2.1 and UC2.2 run asynchronously, meaning that they immediately return the response to the user (e.g. a data provider who started the analysis) without waiting the analysis to be completed (which may take up to several minutes), where the returned response information can be used to later check the status of the analysis, i.e., whether it is still running or has already finished. In particular, the services generate and return the Universally Unique Identifier (UUID), using the uuid Python library. The UUID, as its name implies, is a unique id assigned to the current analysis. It is saved to the MySQL DB using the MySQL Service component, when the analysis is started, and deleted from the MySQL DB after the analysis is finished. Using the returned UUID right after the analysis is started, a user can later call another HTTP REST endpoint, which is configured in the given predictive maintenance services, to check if the analysis is finished. The service of UC1.1 takes 5 seconds to run, so it runs synchronously and returns the produced results in the response.

Each service running in the Kubernetes has its own Git repository, where the code is kept updated and maintained, and the deployment of the service code to Kubernetes is done using the Jenkins jobs. Jenkins, as a deployment automation server, is installed on the AIT Kubernetes infrastructure as well, and for each service deployment, one Jenkins job is configured. After modifying the services code in the corresponding Git repositories, the services need to be redeployed to Kubernetes, using the configured Jenkins job. Figure 13 and Figure 14 show the Kubernetes and Jenkins UIs, respectively. The Kubernetes UI is used to monitor the services, i.e. their availability, logs, resources, etc. or to manage their work, e.g. stop, restart, delete, or update the services. The Jenkins UI is used to configure the Jenkins jobs, which deploy the services from their Git repositories to the Kubernetes infrastructure, i.e. allocate the resources, create Docker images from the source code, set the required Kubernetes parameters, etc.

Figure 13: Kubernetes UI used for monitoring and managing the running services and their resources

Figure 14: Jenkins UI for configuring the jobs for deploying the services to Kubernetes

As mentioned above, at the beginning and at the end of the prediction analysis in the services, the input data and the results are read and stored to and from the InfluxDB component running in the DS. The communication between the Influx DB component and the Kubernetes services is implemented using the influxdb_client Python library. The details about the location of the data in the InfluxDB (e.g. the organization and the buckets names), are communicated through the HTTP REST request body, in the request for triggering the analysis. Figure 15 shows the InfluxDB UI, which is used to monitor and manage the input and output data, used for the prediction analysis.

Figure 15: Influx DB UI used for monitoring and managing the input and output data

Table 17 shows the deployment resources assigned to the services in Kubernetes. Min and Max replicas describe the minimum and maximum number of replicas or pods assigned to the services during auto scaling. Pods represent scheduling units in Kubernetes that serves as the context for that Docker containers, with its own namespace, storage volumes, and configuration data. Memory request and limit represent the minimum amount of memory in megabytes (MB) assigned during the deployment of the service and the maximum amount of memory that can be assigned to the service to run the given request or load. The CPU request and limit represent, similarly as for the memory resources, the amount of the CPU resources assigned to the services,

with 1CPU=1000 units. The resources assigned to the services are based on the total amount of resources available, the complexity of the analysis and models used in the services and the fact that the services may sometimes have higher load or demand either in terms of the processed data or the number of requests to be served.

Table 17: Kubernetes deployment resources allocated to the respective services.

Service	Min Replicas	Max Replicas	Memory Request (MB)	Memory Limit (MB)	CPU Request (1CPU = 1000)	CPU Limit (1CPU = 1000)
UC1 - Refinery	1	2	2000	3000	100	500
UC2.1 – WT Generator (ML)	1	2	10000	15000	400	5000
UC2.1 – WT Generator (DL)	1	2	10000	15000	400	15000
UC2.2 - WT Blades	1	2	10000	15000	400	15000

Table 18 summarizes the average execution times (μ) and corresponding standard deviations (σ) of the services, based on ten consecutive runs. The measurements include three key components: the time required to read input data from the InfluxDB, the processing or analysis time, and the time needed to write the results back to the InfluxDB. As shown in Table 18, the reading times from the InfluxDB are slightly higher for the “UC1 Refinery” and “UC2.1 WT Blades” services compared to the other two. This difference can be attributed to the larger volume and complexity of the input data processed by these services. Specifically, the “UC1 Refinery” service accesses a greater number of sensor data streams, while the “UC2.1 WT Blades” service retrieves two distinct data types—SCADA and climate data—from separate buckets within the InfluxDB. The time range of the input data used in these measurements is 1 month for the services of UC2.1 and UC2.2, while the UC1 service uses a fixed time range of 10 days. The analysis times for the “UC2.1 – WT Generator (DL)” and “UC2.2 – WT Blades” services are significantly higher than for the other two services. This difference arises probably because the latter are based on simpler machine learning models, whereas the other two rely on computationally intensive deep learning architectures. Notably, the “UC2.2 – WT Blades” service requires approximately eight times longer processing time than the “UC2.1 – WT Generator (DL)” service, despite both employing similar deep learning models. This can be attributed to the larger number of input features used by the “UC2.2 – WT Blades” service to detect anomalies, resulting in increased computational load. Currently, all services operate on CPUs, as the deep learning-based services are not time-critical. However, integrating GPUs into the Kubernetes cluster in the future could substantially accelerate the analysis process. Finally, the writing times to the InfluxDB are relatively uniform across all services, since they produce similar types and volumes of output data, such as forecasts of relevant values and detected anomalies.

Table 18: Running times of the services (μ - mean, σ - standard deviation)

Service	InfluxDB read duration [s]	Analysis time [s]	InfluxDB write duration [s]
UC1 - Refinery	$\mu=19.074$ $\sigma=0.512$	$\mu=5.912$ $\sigma=0.666$	$\mu=0.220$ $\sigma=0.030$
UC2.1 - WT Generator (ML)	$\mu=5.064$ $\sigma=0.602$	$\mu=1.269$ $\sigma=0.117$	$\mu=1.242$ $\sigma=0.154$

UC2.1 - WT Generator (DL)	$\mu=1.918$ $\sigma=0.502$	$\mu=49.007$ $\sigma=0.236$	$\mu=1.418$ $\sigma=0.276$
UC2.2 - WT Blades	$\mu=16.905$ $\sigma=1.288$	$\mu=405.176$ $\sigma=2.379$	$\mu=1.383$ $\sigma=0.071$

The assigned service resources can be flexibly scaled by adjusting the Kubernetes resource configurations, which are managed through the previously described Jenkins deployment jobs. The corresponding deployment scripts within these jobs allow autonomous control over the allocation of computational resources, ensuring efficient and balanced utilization across services. Resource usage and service performance are continuously monitored via the Kubernetes Dashboard, providing a basis for data-driven adjustments. When necessary, resource parameters in the deployment scripts can be updated, and the services can be redeployed with the revised configurations to maintain optimal performance and scalability.

6 Added Value of Data-Space-Driven Predictive Maintenance as a Service

For both use cases, DS-enabled services provide tangible added value for all participating stakeholders. The value propositions are analyzed per UC to assess their relevance under real operational conditions, thereby validating the practical benefits of integrating DS with predictive maintenance services. A consolidated overview of the most relevant value propositions and their applicability across the two UCs is presented in Table 19. This section is based on the work documented in more detail in [22].

6.1 Refinery use-case

The UNDERPIN DS enables trusted, real-time interaction between MOH, as the refinery operator and data provider, and SPH, as the predictive analytics service provider. Data exchange between the two entities is achieved via certified EDC connectors, allowing secure, policy-compliant transmission of operational data without exposing the refinery's internal network. All data transfers are aligned with EU Data Governance Act and Data Act. This ensures both technical and legal interoperability, an essential feature for critical manufacturing assets operating under strict cybersecurity and compliance frameworks.

Within this setup, large volumes of time-series data from pressure, temperature, vibration, and displacement sensors are streamed from refinery units through the DS to SPH's predictive maintenance service. The service applies time-series forecasting and anomaly detection to anticipate behaviour shifts over a 24-hour horizon. Outputs from the model, including anomaly scores and predicted degradation patterns, are returned through the connector and visualized on the dashboard developed in the DS.

Through this workflow, maintenance engineers can correlate identified anomalies with process data, cross-check with external conditions or maintenance logs, and initiate targeted interventions when needed. The modular connector setup allows SPH to re-use the same integration architecture across multiple clients, while MOH benefits from an interoperable and sovereign data-sharing environment that supports both on-premise analytics and cloud-based service execution. This arrangement demonstrates how the DS-driven Predictive Maintenance as a Service (PMaaS) approach enhances asset reliability, reduces unplanned downtime, and enables scalable deployment of AI-driven monitoring across industrial domains.

6.2 Wind farm use-case

The UNDERPIN DS enables seamless cooperation between MORE, as the wind farm operator, and AIT, as the provider of predictive maintenance services. Data exchange between the two entities is easily realized through the DS connectors, which allow secure communication without requiring direct access to the operator's infrastructure, which is an essential feature for critical assets.

Using the connectors ensures both technical and legal interoperability, simplifying not only the data exchange but also compliance with the EU Data Governance Act and Data Act, as well as other regulatory frameworks. In this UC, however, a challenge arises from the limited availability of actual component failure data, as for example only four blade failures have been recorded at the wind farm in UC2.2. Since training supervised machine learning models typically requires

many failure examples, additional data sources may be needed. UNDERPIN facilitates this by enabling access to high-quality, interoperable datasets that can be merged for model training.

Furthermore, integrating climate data (e.g., from Copernicus) enhances predictive maintenance, particularly for components such as blades that are affected by severe weather. When the DS provides such external data, it can be easily combined with SCADA data. The resulting trained models are then used to determine generator failures or blade damage in daily operations.

In this specific UC, bi-weekly periods of operational data are submitted to the service provider, which runs the predictive model and returns the identified anomalies through the connector. These results are visualized on the dashboard, supporting the operator in interpreting and acting on them. When an anomaly is detected, the operator first checks external conditions that might explain the anomaly without indicating a technical issue. If no external cause is identified, the operator verifies whether the model may have produced a false alarm due to sensor faults or communication errors. If needed, on-site inspections are conducted, and the operator coordinates with the vendor to perform additional checks. This structured process ensures timely detection and intervention, minimizing downtime and improving the reliability of wind turbine operations.

AIT, as the service provider, benefits from the secure and standardized data-sharing infrastructure of the DS, which enables trustworthy exchange of operational wind turbine data between stakeholders. This framework ensures compliance with data sovereignty and cybersecurity requirements—crucial when handling sensitive industrial assets. Moreover, by providing a unified and interoperable interface for data exchange, the DS allows AIT to efficiently collaborate with multiple customers using the same integration setup, thereby reducing onboarding complexity and enabling scalable deployment of predictive maintenance services. UNDERPIN also accelerates the deployment of predictive maintenance services, shortening the time to market for AI-based monitoring and anomaly detection tools. Moreover, the UC demonstrates how participation within the DS allows providers to expand their service portfolio with advanced predictive analytics and decision-support capabilities, thereby strengthening their market position in the wind energy domain.

Table 19: Summary of value propositions for different stakeholder roles and their applicability in the two use cases.

Data Provider Value Propositions	UC1	UC2	Data Consumer Value Propositions	UC1	UC2
Simplified data sharing and management	✓	✓	Immediate access to relevant and high-quality datasets	✓	✓
Expanded visibility	✗	✗	Scalable access to large, high-quality data sources	✓	✓
Full control over data usage and ownership	✓	✓	Trusted and standardized environment for data exchange	✓	✓
Access to advanced analytics and AI services	✓	✓	Data Interoperability	✗	✓
Opportunities for data monetization	✗	✗	Seamless integration of heterogeneous data sources	✓	✓
Reuse of shared data for multiple applications	✗	✓	Compliance with EU Regulations	✓	✓
Compliance with EU Regulations	✓	✓			
Service Provider Value Propositions	UC1	UC2	Service Provider Value Propositions	UC1	UC2

Trusted and compliant mechanisms for data exchange	✓	✓	Accelerated deployment of new services	✓	✓
Enhanced market presence and recognition	✗	✗	On-demand analytics and insights delivery	✓	✗
Broader portfolio of data-driven services	✓	✓			

7 Validation of infrastructure through the Use Cases

The validation activities aimed to demonstrate that the DS infrastructure developed within the project operates as intended across the different industrial domains represented by the refinery and wind farm pilots. Validation covered both functional and non-functional aspects of the deployed architecture, ensuring that the core components, data management services, and security mechanisms collectively support the end-to-end workflows required by the use cases. The process focused on verifying interoperability, performance, scalability, and compliance of the system under realistic operational conditions, using actual datasets and services implemented in the pilots. The following subsections present the main outcomes of the validation exercises, structured along the key dimensions of system functionality, from component-level verification to overall operational readiness and security assurance.

7.1 Core Components Validation

The validation procedure verified the functionality and integration of core components of the architecture deployed in the DS. The Authority Portal effectively supported user authentication, data asset registration, and contract management interfaces for both the refinery and the wind farm operators. The EDC Connectors, a collection of application programming interfaces, facilitated secure and policy-compliant data transfers between MORE wind farm operations and AIT predictive maintenance services without the need for unique infrastructure access, demonstrating technical and legal interoperability. The DAPS component issued authentication tokens and enforced attribute-based access control in all use case interactions, keeping sovereignty boundaries as described in D2.2.

The central time-series database built on InfluxDB received streams of sensor data from refinery compressors and SCADA systems for wind turbines with different time granularity. Data ingestion to the time-series database occurred at five-minute granularity for historical data and at one-minute granularity for pre-incident or recent data, while supporting both Flux and SQL-style queries for analytics services. The DS also provided data quality assessment services which introduced preliminary assessment of common data quality issues, such as missing values, timestamp corrections, and format issues, prior to data exchange so that the data could be cleaned and pre-processed proactively.

7.2 Semantic Interoperability Validation

The Vocabulary Hub and semantic layer showcased their value in reconciling heterogeneous industrial data. Multiple manufacturers use different combinations of sensors, measurement, and data structures - introducing a new integration complexity. The semantic layer overcame this challenge by providing ontologies and RDF-based (Resource Description Frameworks) vocabularies, which represented a formal semantic description, resulting in the ability of predictive maintenance services to interpret the data in a standardized way for equipment manufactured by different companies. This semantic interoperability was crucial when integrating SCADA operational data with external climate data, using Copernicus ERA5, to establish the advancement for predicting blade failure, automating the conversion and alignment of data formats through ontology mappings.

7.3 Service Integration and Workflow Validation

The infrastructure effectively supported workflows that enable services to operate from "end to end". The predictive maintenance services were containerized and deployed into Kubernetes

clusters. These services exposed Flask-based REST APIs that received input data and, relying on the corresponding trained machine learning models, performed analyses and provided results back to the client asynchronously. The services communicated with the InfluxDB component using the influxdb-client Python library. The services read the input data when the analysis was triggered and stored the results of the analyses back into configured buckets in InfluxDB upon completion.

The connectors offered by the EDC capabilities acted as brokers to forward the HTTP calls to the end point of the services as defined in the data asset contracts. In addition, the workflows ensured that the internal infrastructure detail was not revealed when asset operators triggered predictive maintenance analysis through connector registration processes. Efforts included informing operators of detected anomalies and predicting future behavior of equipment. The results were displayed to the residents in DS dashboards that were specifically designed so that operators would be able to develop understanding of the findings from the analyses and share results with maintenance vendors for planning.

7.4 Operational Readiness Validation

The infrastructure has shown its operational readiness by executing multiple data ingestion, data processing, and data analysis cycles. UC1.1 took historical sensor data from 2017-2020 and more recent data from 2022-2024, processing datasets of various temporal granularities, ranging from 1-minute to 5-minute periods. UC2.1 processed 2,927,958 valid data samples from wind turbine operations, only excluding periods when the turbine was offline and periods of abnormal power production behavior. Model training was performed on 1,662,572 data samples meeting normal operational condition criteria.

Pipelines for automated data preprocessing sorted and addressed common data quality issues, including timestamp fixing, missing value imputation, and exclusion of outage periods (i.e., 60 days before and 7 days after repairs for blade failures; 14 days before and 7 days after for failures of other components). With this preprocessing, the level of quality was assured that some training datasets for the models met criteria for representing only normal operational conditions, thus increasing reliability in the models.

7.5 Scalability and Real-Time Performance

The infrastructure confirmed its capability to enable near-real-time analytics. The predictive maintenance services processed operational data for 24-hour periods, detecting anomalies and delivering results for subsequent visualization on a dashboard for operational decision-making purposes. The asynchronous service architecture enabled user requests to receive immediate response while model inference computations ran in the background tasking threads. Each worker thread had a unique thread id stored in MySQL databases and used for retrieving task status.

The Kubernetes deployment architecture with horizontal pod autoscaling showed scalable performance enabling multiple wind turbines and refinery equipment analysis to run in parallel. Services would automatically scale dependent on workload per organizational constraints, while response time guarantees were met.

7.6 Security and Compliance Validation

The DS framework enforced necessary security and compliance measures throughout the execution of the UCs. The authentication and authorization flows provided by Keycloak ensured that only authorized UC participants access operationally sensitive data. The use of contract-

based data sharing through EDC Connectors ensures data sovereignty with usage policies enforced at both control and data planes. Audit trails all documented all access to and transfer of the data, which ensured compliance with regulations as well as operational transparency.

8 Lessons learned

8.1 Lessons learned for the Data Space

Semantic Layer

Data sharing with clear semantic descriptions is crucial for an effective implementation of predictive maintenance ML models. Each manufacturer may use different sensors, measurements and data formats, which makes it difficult to harmonize and integrate the data without formal definitions of the meaning.

By employing standardized ontologies, stakeholders can efficiently and in a unified way access relevant data, streamlining the integration process and facilitating predictive maintenance training data on a large scale, thereby potentially increasing the quality of the predictions.

The Vocabulary Hub is defined in the IDS-RAM as a basic building block to achieve semantic interoperability in DSs by provisioning common vocabularies. Vocabularies are expressed in RDFs and use RDF Schema (RDFS) and Web Ontology Language (OWL) for ontologies, and Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) for thesauri. The IDS-RAM allows for extending the function of the Vocabulary Hub towards providing ontology mappings that enable DS connectors to automatically convert data between user-specific and standard data formats. Additionally, these standardizations create a shared language across different industry players, reducing misunderstandings and ensuring each participant interprets data in the same way. Such automatic conversions can be performed by Data Transformation Apps by the Data Consumer, the Data Provider, or both. This interoperability is key for achieving cross-functional insights, enabling more effective diagnostics and maintenance recommendations.

We see the need for a Semantic Layer for DSs to provide such vocabulary-based services for advanced and automated semantic description of metadata and data.

Architectural Integration

The focus of the UNDERPIN UCs is to provide predictive maintenance services in a DS based on the consolidated data of multiple DS participants. The idea is to achieve higher quality of predictive services with higher amounts of training data for the ML algorithms. There is the need to eventually consolidate all the training data available in the DS into one storage to run the training process or to use federated learning approaches which can be especially useful when dealing with sensitive or private information. For UNDERPIN, and because of the harmonization needs via a Semantic Layer, we decided to store the integrated data into a time series database, which makes it easy to assemble specific training data for the predictive maintenance ML. This database selection enables fast querying and retrieval of historical data, which is crucial for developing accurate and responsive predictive models. However, the IDS-RAM is based on principles of decentralization for data sharing, which does not synergize with a central data storage. We can see that we need to have a clear view on the whole system architecture and define what is part of the DS and what is outside the DS, but still part of the UNDERPIN architecture. The DS components will be dedicated to sovereign data sharing, enabling participants to access predictive maintenance services under established contractual terms. Such transparency builds trust among DS participants, encouraging broader data contributions and improving the predictive power of the ML models. Meanwhile, training processes can

proceed independently outside the DS, ensuring transparency and efficiency without compromising decentralized data-sharing principles. This dual approach ensures that while data remains decentralized, its value is maximized through organized, cohesive processing and utilization.

Data Governance and Security

Ensuring data sovereignty and granular access control was a primary consideration in planning the DS, guiding us to define clear policies on who could access, process, and share data, and under what conditions. Compliance with data privacy regulations, was also central to our planning, prompting us to consider data anonymization techniques and a secure framework for data sharing to mitigate risks of unauthorized access. Additionally, we emphasized the importance of real-time auditing and tracking mechanisms in our design to support transparency and accountability in data usage and access. Altogether, these considerations influenced our planning, laying the groundwork for a robust, secure, and compliant DS infrastructure for future data sharing.

8.2 Lessons learned for stakeholder participation

Data Collection

During the implementation of UC2.1 and UC2.2, a key challenge persisted concerning the automation of data collection from the wind farm operator's infrastructure. Accessing data from the wind turbines' SCADA systems, necessary for retrieving sensor readings, fault logs, and operational parameters, requires multiple authentication layers through a dedicated virtual private network (VPN) managed by the manufacturer. This security setup continues to impede automated data transfer, necessitating manual data extraction in batches.

Although this process does not compromise the technical validity of the UCs, it limits scalability and efficiency, particularly when aiming for continuous data-driven services such as predictive maintenance. A potential solution using Robotic Process Automation (RPA) tools was evaluated; however, the operator's cybersecurity team has since confirmed that neither RPA-based access nor other forms of direct connections between the DS and the operator's internal systems are permissible due to strict cybersecurity policies.

This constraint highlights a broader challenge in industrial data-sharing scenarios: the tension between operational security requirements and the European ambition for interoperable, automated data exchange. The experience underscores the need for standardized, secure, and certifiable data access mechanisms, such as trusted connectors or certified intermediary gateways, to enable safe yet automated data sharing between critical infrastructure operators and external service providers.

8.3 Lessons learned for use case implementation

Data Quality

The execution of UCs also revealed several important lessons regarding data quality, a critical aspect for successful predictive maintenance. Data from industrial production systems and other operational sources often exhibits flaws, such as sensor noise, equipment malfunctions, human error, and even export-related issues, such as misalignments, truncation, and format inconsistencies. These challenges were especially evident in the SCADA data used for both use

cases. To address these issues, extensive pre-processing of the data was required before it could be used for analysis. This included correcting timestamp errors, filtering out periods of non-operation, and normalizing sensor readings to ensure consistency across the dataset.

The UNDERPIN DS provided valuable assistance in managing these data quality challenges by offering a service that evaluates the statistical properties of data before its exchange. This service enabled participants to understand the quality of their data early on, which in turn allowed for more efficient pre-processing and reduced the risk of errors in the predictive maintenance models. Additionally, the data-quality assessment tools provided insights into common issues, helping the engineering teams improve data reliability and the accuracy of machine learning models used for predictions.

However, a key challenge remains: the limited availability of high-quality, failure-labeled data. For example, in UC2.2, the available dataset for wind turbine blade failure contained only a small number of events (four recorded failures), which is far less than other studies (e.g., Razamand et al., which used 70 faults across 88 turbines). This underlines the importance of data sharing between stakeholders, as pooling diverse datasets can improve the robustness of predictive models.

Yet, as highlighted by the experiences with UC2.1, gaining access to operational data from vendors-controlled systems (like SCADA) can be hindered by complex relationships between wind farm operators and turbine manufacturers, further restricting data availability. Here, DS have the potential to overcome such barriers by facilitating secure and standardized data exchange, allowing operators to share critical operational data with service providers for model development and predictive maintenance tasks.

9 Conclusion

This deliverable provides the final results of the UNDERPIN use cases (UCs), focusing on the implementation, validation, and outcomes of the predictive maintenance services developed throughout the project. It builds upon the previous (mid-term) version of the deliverable, consolidating the findings and lessons learned across three use cases:

- UC1.1 - Monitoring and predictive maintenance in the refinery,
- UC2.1 - Predictive maintenance in wind farms, and
- UC2.2 - Wind turbine blade repair prediction.

The outcomes of these UCs validate the potential of the UNDERPIN Data Space in enabling data-driven predictive maintenance solutions. Specifically, UC1.1 and UC2.1 demonstrated the practical value of integrating predictive maintenance models with operational systems, enhancing asset management and reducing downtime. UC2.2, while facing challenges due to limited failure data, advanced predictive capabilities using weather data and provided insights into early blade damage detection.

The validation of the UNDERPIN DS infrastructure confirmed its ability to support secure, scalable, and interoperable data exchange across heterogeneous industrial settings. Key aspects of the infrastructure, such as core components, data management services, and security mechanisms, were thoroughly tested and shown to operate effectively in real-world conditions. The integration of machine learning models into the DS framework facilitated seamless prediction workflows and reinforced the value of the UNDERPIN approach.

The lessons learned throughout the project highlight critical success factors, including the importance of data quality management, the need for robust data-sharing protocols, and the challenges of working with diverse industrial data formats. These insights provide a solid foundation for future deployments and offer actionable recommendations for other DS initiatives aiming to leverage predictive maintenance and similar advanced data analytics techniques.

In conclusion, the results of the UNDERPIN project underscore the potential of DS-driven services to enhance the efficiency, scalability, and sustainability of predictive maintenance systems, driving value for stakeholders in critical industrial sectors.

10 Bibliography

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